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WHITE FLY: A CHEMICAL CONTROL

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Abstract

Sun flower is an important oil crop of India and in Bihar it is grown in the summer season. The White fly pest of Sun flower is a common in Bihar. The present investigation is carried out to study the control of white fly using the chemical insecticides alone and in combination and bio insecticides. It has been found that It is found that soil application (basal treatment) of phorate 10 G @ 1.5 kg / ha in combination with two sprayings either of cypermethrin 25 EC @ 0.005 % or methyl-o-demeton 25 EC @ 0.03 % at an interval of 45 and 60 days after sowing were found most effective.

Keywords: Sunflower, White fly, Pesticides

Introduction

Bihar has diversified agriculture production in favour of horticulture and commercial crops at very slower rate during the post-bifurcation period. But, it is important to highlight that the area under food grains still occupies more than 86 percent of total cropped area due to the traditional cropping pattern as well as traditional food habits. Therefore, area, production and yield of non-food grain crops are more stable as compared to food grain crops. Among the agro-climatic Zones in Bihar, highest share in area and production of aghani rice, linseeds, seasamum, pea, gram and lentil . Sunflower is an important short duration crop grown for its edible oils in Bihar . It is a crop of choice for farmers due to its wider adaptability, high yield potential shorter duration and profitability.

There are many insects, pests and diseases causing agents decreasing the production. Whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Genn.) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) is a major pest of many crops

including Sun flower and important vector of geminiviral pathogens worldwide. *B. tabaci* has been considered as a species complex containing numerous genetic and biological variants undergoing continuous evolutionary changes. The Nymphs and adults suck sap and excrete honeydew (Sandhu et al., 1973 and Goel and Kumar, 1990) . A secondary infection develops when a black sooty mould fungus grows on the sticky honeydew. There are no visible damage symptoms with low numbers of whiteflies. Under very heavy infestations, plants lose vigour and damage is manifested under severe moisture stress, causing leaf wilting and failure to set seed.

Whitefly has emerged as the new potential sucking insect pest of sunflower and also acting as the vector of leaf curl begomo virus in Northern Karnataka, India. It affects the productivity of sunflower an important oilseed crop in the country (Katti Pramod, 2007, Basappa, 1998). Sunflower leaf curl disease vectored by whitefly was noticed for the first time in the country and the disease was recorded on sunflower hybrid ‘Sun breed-275’ up to 40 per cent disease incidence in the fields of Main Agricultural Research Station, University of Agricultural Sciences, Raichur, Northern Karnataka, during rabi season of 2009 (Govindappa *et al.*, 2011). Since then, the whitefly infestation has been noticed in an endemic form consecutively for the last two years in sunflower growing areas of northern districts of Karnataka.

The present investigation has been conducted during 2012-13 and 2013-14 in Supal area of Bihar to find out the suitable methods for control of White fly. The variety of sunflower KBSH 44 was and number of chemical, biological insecticides was used alone and in combination. At the end the production was calculated in relation to insecticides.

Methodology:

The field studies were carried out on occurrence and abundance of whitefly pests on sunflower, and observations were conducted on sunflower, *Helianthus annuus* L., crop during whole growing season. The experiment was conducted in randomized completely block design replicated four times.

Twenty five plants were randomly selected from each block of sunflower crop, five leaves were selected, two from bottom portion, while, two from middle and one from top of plant, and the pest population were counted with the help of magnifying glass.

The present investigation on insecticidal trial against major insect pests of sunflower (cultivar Modern) was undertaken during the two consecutive years *i.e.* 2012-13 and 2013-14 in summer season.

Results & Discussion

It is found that soil application (basal treatment) of phorate 10 G @ 1.5 kg / ha in combination with two sprayings either of cypermethrin 25 EC @ 0.005 % or methyl-o-demeton 25 EC @ 0.03 % at an interval of 45 and 60 days after sowing were found most effective in checking the white fly incidence, though they did not differ significantly among themselves and elicited 1.02 and 1.34 whiteflies/ leaf, respectively.

Table 1: Population of Whitefly in Sunflower.

Date of observation	No. of plants observed	No. of whiteflies	Temperature	R .H%
15.2.12	25	1.25±0.1	18.07	56.85
22.2.12		2.41±0.38	19.42	56.85
29.2.12		4.25±0.51	20.57	60.0
5.3.12		4.59±0.51	21.64	61.57
12.3.12		6.65±0.65	22.27	62.57
19.2.13		7.55±0.31	23.47	63.57
26.2.13		7.20±0.00	24.5	65.67
5.3.13		9.1±0.25	27.48	65.28
12.3.13		10.2±0.70	28.72	64.42
19.3.13		10.51±0.8	29.07	61.0
26.3.13		12.72±0.89	30.35	64.27
2.4.13		14.69±0.74	30.37	65.27
9.4.13		17.77±0.78	31.51	65.87

Good coverage of the underside of leaves is essential for effective use of insecticides against whiteflies. Immature whiteflies do not move, so the insecticide must reach them at their feeding sites (Rangarajan et al., 1975; Sandhu et al., 1973). Canopy penetration can be improved

by better spacing of plants. Because of difficulties in obtaining complete coverage, resistance problems, and because not all whitefly stages are equally sensitive to all materials, multiple applications are usually required. Rotating between chemical classes when making multiple applications for whiteflies is recommended to reduce development of resistance.

Successful management of whiteflies requires an integrated program that focuses on prevention and relies on cultural and biological control methods when possible.

Table 2 : Effect of insecticidal schedules against White fly *Bemisia tabaci* Genn.

Sl. No.	Treatments	Whitefly population/leaf	
		Summer 2012	Summer 2013
T-1	Phorate + Methyl-o-demeton	1.34	1.22
T-2	Phorate + Endosulfan	2.42	2.10
T-3	Phorate + Monocrotophos	1.42	1.12
T-4	Phorate + Cypermethrin	1.02	0.80
T-5	Phorate + Neemazal	2.52	2.21
T-6	Phorate + Biolep	3.39	3.15
T-7	Methyl-o-demeton	3.36	3.33
T-8	Endosulfan	3.42	3.21
T-9	Monocrotophos	2.81	2.25
T-10	Cypermethrin	2.97	2.33
T-11	Neemazal	7.75	6.83
T-12	Biolep	17.58	15.97
T-13	Control	19.0	17.0

In summer sunflower crop during 2012, basal application of phorate with two sprayings of monocrotophos registered the highest crop yield and it was as high as 1380.00 and 1362.500 kg/ha. Although it was found at par when compared with phorate + biolep, phorate + endosulfan, phorate + methyl-odemeton and phorate with two sprayings of cypermethrin in the summer sunflower and these treatments manifested the yield of crop to the tune of 1375.500, 1370.100, 1336.500 and 1331.500 kg/ ha, respectively which was statistically non significant among themselves. Remaining treatments responded intermediary on the crop yield which ranged from

980.500 to 1000.00 kg/ ha when were used alone. Phorate + two sprayings of any tested insecticides in present investigation. Biolep registered highest yield of 1365.500 kg/ ha. No doubt it was found statistically at par with mono crotophos or endosulfan, methyl-o-demeton and cypermethrin. The performance of rest of the alone sprayings of used insecticides noticed their poorer performance regarding total yield of sunflower. Kumar *et al.* (2008) also found highest grain yield from oxydemeton methyl @ 0.025 % treatment which was due to effective control of linseed bud fly.

References:

- Basappa, H. 1998. Strategies for insect pest management in sunflower. In: Abstracts- International Conference on Pest and Pesticide Management for Sustainable Agriculture, 11-13 December, 1998, C.S.A. University of Agriculture and Technology, Kanpur, India. 374p.
- Goel, S.C, and Kumar, A. 1990. Insect pests and predators associated to sunflower in winter of northern India. *Indian Journal of Entomology*. 52:39-45.
- Govindappa, M. R., Shankergoud, I., Shankarappa, K. S., Wickramaarachchi, W. A. R. T., Anjeneya Reddy, B. and Rangaswamy, K. T., 2011. Molecular detection and partial characterization of begomovirus associated with leaf curl disease of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus*) in Southren India. *Plant Pathol. J.*, 10 (1): 29-35.
- Katti, P., 2000. Sucking pests of sunflower with special reference to *Thrips palmi* Karny, its relation with necrosis virus and management. *Ph.D. Thesis, Univ. Agric. Sci. Dharwad* (India). pp:108-112.
- Kumar, M., Ali, S. and Mishra, M.K., 2008. Population dynamics of linseed insect pests and management of *Dasyneura lini* Barnes. *Ann. Pl. Protec. Sci.*, 16 (2): 289- 293.
- Rangarajan, A.V., Mahadevan, N.R, and Iyemperumal, S. 1975. Pest complex of sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* Linn.) in Tamil Nadu. *Indian Journal of Entomology*. 37:188-189.
- Sandhu, G.S., Brar, K.S, and Bhalla, J.S. 1973. Pests of sunflower and other insects associated with sunflower crop. *Oilseeds J*. 3:19-26.